

DATA SCIENCE TECHNIQUES FOR ANALYZING NOTE TRENDS AND BRAND PROGRESSION IN THE PERFUME INDUSTRY

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Abstract - In the modern perfume industry, limited feedback on products can obstruct accurate market analysis and trend forecasting. This paper introduces an alternative rating strategy using a dataset from Fragnatica, which reveals significant gaps in available ratings for a wide range of perfumes. To address these inconsistencies, we developed a comprehensive pipeline using data science techniques for cleaning, filtering, and clustering fragrance data. By applying text analysis methods like Word2Vec and cosine similarity, we measured relationships between fragrance notes and employed K-Means clustering to group them into coherent categories. Cluster weights were calculated based on occurrence of fragrance notes, while designer performance was assessed by examining how often their perfumes appeared in the dataset. This approach offers deeper insights into fragrance trends and designer influence, providing a better understanding of market dynamics and product evaluations.

Keywords - Data Science, Natural Language Processing, Perfume Industry, Trend Analysis, Text Similarity, Clustering.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the recent times, online product reviews have become increasingly important in the modern perfume industry, significantly influencing consumer behavior and market dynamics. As consumers turn to the internet for guidance, they rely heavily on reviews, ratings, and detailed descriptions to make informed purchasing decisions. These online assessments not only shape consumer perceptions but also drive market trends, providing valuable insights for manufacturers and marketers.

However, the reliability of ratings is often compromised due to inconsistencies and missing entries, which can distort the true picture of consumer preferences. During our examination of the product feedback problem, we came across a dataset from Fragnatica that illustrates this challenge. This dataset contains over 80,000 entries, however, more than 90% of them have empty string entries for the rating column. This discovery motivated us to explore alternative ways to assess and rate perfume products, specifically focusing on leveraging other available data within the dataset, such as list of included fragrance notes and some basic designer information.

In response to this gap, this paper proposes an alternative system designed to address the limitations of missing ratings. Our main goal is to develop a data processing pipeline that thoroughly cleans, clusters, and analyzes fragrance notes and designer information in the dataset. By employing sophisticated data science techniques, including text similarity measures and clustering algorithms, we derive a compound score for each perfume that acts as a surrogate for the missing rating. This scoring

system provides a more detailed and refined evaluation metric that captures the specific characteristics and market potential of each perfume. This unified scoring approach bridges the void left by absent ratings and offers deeper insights into market trends and consumer preferences. By concentrating on intrinsic attributes like fragrance notes and designer reputation, our methodology delivers a comprehensive representation of each product, uncovering potential market dynamics that might be overlooked due to the lack of explicit ratings.

Ultimately, the proposed study offers a more data-driven strategy for overall fragrance evaluation, aiding consumers, industry professionals, and promoters in understanding and navigating the complex landscape of perfume selection and marketing. By establishing a systematic method for perfume rating in the absence of direct user feedback, this research lays the foundation for more advanced analysis and predictive modeling in the perfume industry.

II. METHODOLOGY

In the following section, we detail the structured methodology employed to build an alternative scoring system for perfumes, leveraging the fragrance notes and designer information from the given dataset. The approach involves several important steps, including data collection and cleaning, fragrance notes extraction and preprocessing, text similarity analysis, clustering, and scoring. The ultimate objective is to create a compound score that serves as a reliable proxy for the missing ratings. The steps are outlined in the following subsections.

2.1. Data Collection and Cleaning

The dataset utilized in this study comprises a vast number of entries related to perfumes. The columns included in the dataset are title, description, rating, notes, designer, url, and aset of reviews. Each column contains valuable information relevant to perfume evaluation. However, we decided to choose columns such as title, description, rating, notes and designer for this version of the study. Link to the perfume profile (on the Fragnatica website) is not considered as highly important at this moment, also we are skipping the data in review column, since it is fetched from a very large collection of individual user reviews, so it contains a lot of damaged and incomplete records.

Furthermore, upon initial inspection, we realized that while there are no null values in the columns, a significant issue was observed with the rating column. Specifically, this column contained numerous empty strings, which posed a challenge for deeper analysis. In contrast, only a minor fraction of

missing data was detected in other columns, like in title and description. Data bundles of review data andlinks of perfumes are discarded for now.

To properly address the issue of missing data only in rating column, rows with incomplete entries in the title or description columns were removed from the dataset. For the rating column, where the issue was more prevalent, we opted to convert missing ratings into numerical values. Missing ratings were assigned a starting value of 0. This conversion facilitated the application of our alternative scoring system, which aims to develop legitimate ratings ranging from 1 to 5. The final scores are rounded to one decimal place, in alignment with the beginning rating scale proposed in the dataset. Existing ratings remained unchanged.

By implementing the described steps, we prepared the dataset for further processing, ensuring that the remaining data is both complete and suitable for the subsequent development of a robust scoring system.

```

RangeIndex: 84142 entries, 0 to 84141
Data columns (total 5 columns):
#   Column          Non-Null Count  Dtype
---  ---            -
0   rating          84142 non-null  object
1   notes           84142 non-null  object
2   designer        84142 non-null  object
3   description     84142 non-null  object
4   title           84142 non-null  object
    
```

Fig 1. Basic Dataset Information

```

Column      Empty_Count
0   rating      81668
1   notes       0
2   designer    0
3   description 8
4   title       8
    
```

Fig 2. Missing (Empty) Values per Column

2.2. Notes Extraction and Preprocessing

Assigned fragrance notes, represented as strings, were extracted and preprocessed to standardize and reduce the data variability. This included tokenization, lemmatization, and the removal of stop words using

Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK) library. The goal was to create a uniform representation of all notes, facilitating effective similarity analysis. Unique notes were identified, and their frequencies were calculated in Python, providing the basis for detailed exploring.

2.2.1. Tokenization

Tokenization involves splitting given fragrance notes into individual words or tokens. This step is fundamental for transforming text into a format that can be easily analyzed and processed later. Using the mentioned NLTK library, the notes were tokenized to separate them into manageable units. For instance, if the input text is "This perfume is a delightful blend of citrus and floral notes", the tokenized output would be: ['This', 'perfume', 'is', 'a', 'delightful', 'blend', 'of', 'citrus', 'and', 'floral', 'notes', '.']

2.2.2. Lemmatization

Lemmatization reduces words to their base or root form. This step is crucial for standardizing variations of words, which helps in reducing the complexity of text and improving the accuracy of similarity analysis. For example, the words like "flowering" and "flowers" would both be reduced to "flower".

2.2.3. Removal of Stop Words

Stop words are common words (e.g. "and", "the", "is") that are often removed from text as they do not contribute meaningful information for the analysis. Using NLTK, stop words were filtered out from the tokenized and lemmatized fragrance notes to focus on more relevant terms.

2.2.4. Unique Notes and Frequencies

After preprocessing, the notes were transformed into a uniform representation. This process contains combining tokens into phrases or maintaining them as individual terms, depending on the level of granularity required. Obtained uniform representation facilitated effective comparison and clustering of notes.

After that, unique fragrance notes were extracted from the preprocessed textual data. Every note was considered as a distinct entity, and its frequency of occurrence across all perfumes was calculated. The frequency of each unique note i was determined as:

$$f_i = \frac{n_i}{N}$$

where n_i is the count of occurrences of note i and N is the total number of notes. This calculation supports further analysis, including clustering and scoring.

2.2.5. Handling Variability

To address variability in note representation, any synonyms or related terms were standardized. For instance, terms such as "citrus" and "lemon" were unified under a common label. This step was crucial to make sure that similar notes were grouped together, enhancing the accuracy of the clustering process.

2.3. Text Similarity and Clustering

Having completed the procedures for tokenization and lemmatization of fragrance notes, the next step was to measure their similarities and cluster them into meaningful groups. This approach contains stages like computing text similarity, performing clustering, and assigning cluster labels and scores.

To assess the similarity between fragrance notes, we used the cosine similarity, a common metric for evaluating the similarity between text vectors. Cosine similarity calculates the cosine of the angle between two vectors in a multi-dimensional space, providing a score that ranges from 0 (no similarity) to 1 (identical). This measure helps us determine how closely related different fragrance notes are. The formula for cosine similarity (labeled as COSIM for this paper) between two vectors A and B is:

$$\text{COSIM}(A, B) = \frac{A \cdot B}{|A||B|} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i \times B_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i^2} \times \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n B_i^2}}$$

where A_i and B_i are components of vectors A and B . This measure ranges from -1 (completely dissimilar) to 1 (identical), with higher values indicating greater similarity.

To represent perfume notes as vectors, we utilized Word2Vec embeddings from the Gensim library for Python. Word2Vec technique generates continuous vector representations of words, capturing semantic meanings based on their context in a corpus. This approach allows us to map fragrance notes into a high-dimensional space where similar notes are positioned closely together.

To cluster the notes into coherent groups, we used the K-Means clustering algorithm, implemented via scikit-learn library in Python. The main objective of K-Means is to partition the given data into k clusters, while minimizing the variance within each cluster. Mathematically, K-Means algorithm aims to minimize the following cost function:

$$J = \sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i^{(j)} - \mu_j|^2$$

where $x_i^{(j)}$ represents the data in points of cluster j and μ_j is the centroid of cluster j .

Prior to clustering, all vectors were standardized using StandardScaler, also from scikit-learn library, to ensure all features contributed equally to the clustering process. We opted for ten clusters based on initial exploratory analysis, and every cluster was labeled according to the most frequent note within it. In results section, we attached graphs for showing these clusters with their labels and distribution of included notes.

2.4. Scoring Fragrance Clusters and Designers

To evaluate the significance of each fragrance cluster, we introduced a weighted scoring system. The weight of each cluster is determined based on the number of notes it encompasses. Specifically, the desired weight was successfully computed as the ratio of the number of notes within the cluster to the total number of unique notes, scaled to a range of 1 to 5.

This method ensures that clusters with a larger number of representative notes are given a higher weight, reflecting their increased significance. The weighted cluster scores provide better insights into the distribution and importance of main fragrance features throughout the dataset.

Right after calculating the weighted scores for note clusters, we assessed the compound note scores for each perfume by averaging weights of the clusters associated with its notes. For instance, if a perfume's notes are associated with clusters weighted at 2.5, 3.5, and 3.3, the compound note score would be equal to their average, which is 3.1. This type of score provides a unified measure of the fragrance profile.

Additionally, designer names were analyzed to determine their presence and popularity based on the frequency of their perfumes. Designer scores were likewise adjusted on a scale from 1 to 5 to represent their influence on the market. Illustrations of designer distributions are included in the results section.

2.5. Developing the Compound Scoring System

Finally, to synthesize the information from both fragrance clusters and designers, a compound score was developed. This score was evaluated as a weighted sum of its compound cluster score for fragrance notes and designer influence. The compound score S_p for a perfume p is given by:

$$S_p = \alpha \cdot S_{c(p)} + \beta \cdot I_{d(p)},$$

where $S_{c(p)}$ is the total compound score of the cluster containing perfume p , $I_{d(p)}$ is the influence score of its designer $d(p)$, and α and β are weights assigned to each perfume component, reflecting their importance in the overall evaluation.

For this version of the analysis, we decided to go with $\alpha = 0.6$ for note score and $\beta = 0.4$ for designer score. That means, a perfume with a cluster score of 3.1 and a designer score of 3.5 would have a final compound score of 3.3, balancing the contributions of both factors. In the end, the score was imputed to the rating column, effectively providing a substitute value for perfumes with missing original ratings.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Throughout this section, we present the outcomes of our analysis, showcasing several key visualizations that illustrate the effectiveness of implementing the alternative scoring system. The provided results reveal valuable insights into the distribution and clustering of fragrance notes together with varying popularity of different designers within the market.

We begin by demonstrating the distribution and characteristics of fragrance clusters created using K-Means methodology. This process grouped numerous unique notes into ten distinct clusters, each labeled by the most representative note. The following graphics reveal how fragrance notes are organized, including their relative significance, together with cluster scores scaled from 1 to 5, giving insights into note importance and popularity. Each cluster shows a unique olfactory profile, reflecting different fragrance families and their dominant notes.

Fig 3. Clusters with Similar Notes

Next, we present a designer influence chart that highlights the prominence of various designers. This chart shows how designer frequency impacts perfume ratings, with the most prolific designers receiving higher scores. It also demonstrates patterns in purchase preferences and how often specific designers take the lead in the market.

Fig 4. Designer Influence Chart

Finally, we rank the top 10 perfumes based on the alternative ratings derived from our compound scoring system. This ranking illustrates how combining cluster and designer scores provides a refined assessment of perfume quality and market

potential. By addressing inconsistencies caused by missing ratings, this scoring system offers an innovative and improved perspective on perfume evaluation.

Fig 5. Top 10 Perfumes Based on Alternative Ratings

The presented analysis offers meaningful insights into the fragrance market, laying a solid foundation for future advancements. The proposed study successfully identified main clusters of given fragrance notes and evaluated their relative importance using a weighted scoring system. For instance, the clusters featuring Amber and Bergamot as their dominant notes stood out as particularly significant, reflecting prevalent trends and preferences within the whole dataset. Similarly, perfumes from The Dua Brand and Avon company

were featured for their very high alternative ratings, demonstrating the efficacy of our scoring system.

This analysis surely provides a strong basis for integrating machine learning algorithms into fragrance market research. By leveraging the compound note scores and designer influence scores, future work can potentially employ predictive modeling to forecast trends, develop recommendation systems, and refine marketing strategies. Machine learning models can be trained to predict fragrance

preferences based on the existing historical data, improving the capacity to recommend products that align with consumer tastes. Moreover, upcoming development could incorporate investigating deeper correlations and employing more advanced techniques to analyze the contents of user reviews and their sentiments.

Our approach has demonstrated that it is possible to address major deficiencies in data and still generate meaningful product ratings from otherwise incomplete information. This capability is essential for creating an actionable framework in the fragrance industry, where data availability can often be inconsistent.

IV. CONCLUSION

In summary, this study successfully introduced a novel scoring system for fragrances, addressing issues related to incomplete product data and missing ratings. Throughout incorporating weighted cluster scores and compound note scores, we managed to gain a deeper understanding of key fragrance attributes and designer impact. Identifying top designers and note clusters underscores our method's ability to effectively capture market trends and modern consumer preferences. This approach not only addresses anomalies in the original dataset but also provides actionable insights into the fragrance market dynamics, empowering customers and stakeholders to make more informed decisions.

Additionally, given visualizations and employed analytical methods facilitate a nuanced examination of fragrance profiles, revealing the intricate relationships between different fragrance notes and their popularity. Future work will include applying machine learning techniques to improve industry analysis and potential recommendation systems. We will focus on validating our findings with broader datasets and refining our methods to enhance predictive accuracy and market relevance, ultimately aiming to develop a framework adaptable to the evolving fragrance market.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We would like to extend our gratitude to fellow professors and teaching assistants from the Academy of Technical-Educational Vocational Studies for their support throughout this research. We are also deeply grateful to Marina Marjanović, Milena's PhD mentor,

whose guidance and encouragement were invaluable to the successful completion of this study.

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